

How renewable energy mix shapes day-ahead price predictability: A comparative analysis of solar, wind, and biomass in Czechia

Libor Štěpánek^a, Eftichios Koutroulis^b, Hnin Yee Aye^a, Ohn Zin Lin^{a,*} , Dagmar Juchelkova^a

^a Department of Applied Electronics, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, Ostrava, Moravian-Silesian, 70800, Czech Republic

^b School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Technical, University of Crete, Akrotiri Campus, Chania, 73100, Greece

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ABSTRACT

Understanding how renewable energy mixes influence day-ahead electricity price predictability is essential for market operations and renewable integration in thermally dominated systems. This study analyzes one year of hourly data from the Czech electricity market. Five models are evaluated across four renewable-dominance regimes to assess price predictability under observed system conditions. Linear Regression provides the best overall predictive performance across the full sample, while Random Forest is used for regime-specific analysis due to its ability to capture nonlinear interactions. Solar-dominated hours yield the lowest forecasting errors, with Random Forest achieving an RMSE of 10.97 euros per megawatt hour, reflecting the regular diurnal alignment of solar generation with load. Fossil-dominated hours exhibit the highest errors, with an RMSE of 48.53 euros per megawatt hour and frequent extreme price spikes. In comparison, solar-dominated conditions reduce RMSE by approximately 77%. Biomass contributes moderate stabilizing effects, while wind plays a minimal role in price formation. SHAP analysis applied to the Random Forest model shows that higher solar and overall renewable shares are associated with reduced sensitivity of prices to imports and load, alongside persistent lagged-price effects. Seasonal and weekly error patterns confirm that predictability improves when renewable output aligns with demand. The mechanisms identified are applicable to similar thermally dominated, interconnected power systems beyond Czechia. The findings indicate that expanding solar and biomass capacity can stabilize day-ahead prices in flexible thermal systems and support regime-aware decision-making for market operators.

1. Introduction

The rapid growth of variable renewable energy (VRE) sources is significantly impacting European electricity markets, especially concerning short-term price formation and market volatility [1,2]. Day-Ahead Price Forecasting (DAPF) is widely used in practice, but its performance is sensitive to VRE output, load, and cross-border flows [3].

Many studies confirm the strong autoregressive structure of electricity prices, emphasizing the importance of lagged price signals for accurate prediction [4]. Price formation is complex, driven by nonlinear interactions between supply, demand, renewable output, and core market fundamentals [5]. Machine learning (ML) models (like ensemble methods and neural networks) excel at capturing these nonlinear temporal dependencies and provide greater forecasting robustness under variable renewable conditions [6,7]. ML often outperforms traditional

statistical approaches in the highly variable, nonlinear environment of short-term price forecasting [8]. Advanced methods like dimensionality reduction (e.g., PCA) and robust outlier removal are increasingly employed to stabilize forecasting performance in markets with high renewable penetration [9].

Electricity price research typically examines three related but analytically distinct dimensions of market behavior: price levels, price volatility, and price predictability. Price levels refer to the magnitude of the day-ahead market clearing price, while price volatility describes the degree of temporal variation and extreme price fluctuations over time. In contrast, price predictability reflects the extent to which future prices can be accurately forecasted using available explanatory information such as historical prices, load conditions, and generation patterns. Although renewable energy integration can influence all three dimensions, the focus of this study is specifically on price predictability,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ohn.zin.lin@vsb.cz (O.Z. Lin).

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which is evaluated through forecasting errors across different renewable-dominance regimes.

Electricity price volatility is highly regime-dependent, meaning the effect of renewable generation (amplifying or dampening volatility) depends on current system conditions [10]. For instance, solar may reduce volatility in extreme regimes, while other sources like wind or gas have specific, sometimes opposing, regime-dependent effects [10]. Given the distributional changes and volatility caused by rising VRE, recent studies move beyond standard linear or basic ML models. Owolabi et al. [11] analyze renewable energy impacts on price dynamics, while Maticka and Mahmoud [12] develop nonlinear models to capture the corresponding uncertainty. Furthermore, multivariate probabilistic forecasting processes point forecasts into joint price distributions, which helps represent intra-day dependence structures and price-risk profiles [13].

Parallel literature documents how renewable generation reshapes market behavior. However, impacts differ across technologies and markets. For example, a recent study of the Turkish day-ahead market finds that wind and run-of-river generation reduce prices, whereas solar can increase prices because of its lower capacity factor and the design of feed-in support schemes [14]. In a stylized peak-load pricing framework, Antweiler and Muesgens [8] show that the short-term merit-order effect is largely transitory: prices initially fall when renewables enter an unadjusted system, but tend to return to levels consistent with conventional capacity costs once the generation mix re-optimizes. Other analyses highlight how renewable expansion interacts with fuel and carbon markets to shape both average price levels and volatility in interconnected European systems, including evidence from Germany where renewables dampen prices but rising gas and CO₂ prices partly offset this effect [15]. Renewable generation also significantly affects volatility patterns, with nonlinear and system-dependent impacts that vary across markets [16,17]. Biomass deployment also depends on sustainable feedstock availability and economic competitiveness, as shown for perennial energy crops in the Czech Republic [18]. Additional multi-country evidence shows that renewable energy affects extreme positive and negative price fluctuations through nonlinear threshold mechanisms, with stabilizing effects emerging only once renewable penetration exceeds critical levels [19].

Recent studies show that higher renewable penetration can reduce extreme price risks. Ajanaku and Collins [17] analyze wind-generated energy impacts on prices, while Meng et al. [20] model price behavior under high variability of renewable energy production. Forecast errors often display fat-tailed or regime-dependent patterns under variable renewable conditions, complicating market operations and planning [21]. Because volatility shapes investment and risk management, analyzing volatility regimes remains essential [10]. Prior forecasting studies show that model performance can degrade unpredictably under fluctuating renewable conditions [22], enforcing the need for explainability tools that capture nonlinear effects and interactions.

The Czech electricity system is well suited for such analysis. The system is dominated by coal, lignite, and nuclear generation, complemented by moderate solar and biomass output and very limited wind generation [23]. The Czech Republic is highly interconnected with Germany, Slovakia, Poland, and Austria through market coupling [15, 24]. Cross-border exchanges provide an important balancing channel and can amplify or dampen renewable-driven price effects in Central Europe [23]. Recent empirical studies show that volatility spillovers between European electricity markets are significant and that renewable generation, particularly solar, shapes these cross-border risk transmissions [8,22]. Beyond the wholesale market, recent case studies also show that decentralized agrivoltaics and community-energy projects can significantly enhance local energy self-sufficiency and resilience in Czech rural areas [25]. This combination of characteristics provides an opportunity to examine how renewable penetration shapes not only market outcomes but also the difficulty of predicting prices.

Although prior researches highlighted above has examined the merit

order effect, volatility responses, and renewable impacts on electricity price formation, important gaps remain:

1. Few studies link technology-specific renewable dominance regimes to the quantitative difficulty of day-ahead electricity price prediction.
2. Evidence is limited for thermally dominated and strongly interconnected systems, where renewable availability interacts with load and cross-border flows to shape predictability.
3. Only a small number of studies use explainable artificial intelligence to identify the mechanisms through which renewable output modifies price dynamics and prediction errors.
4. Evidence for the Czech day-ahead market remains limited, and this context has not been examined in detail using a regime-based prediction error and explainability framework.

This study addresses these gaps by evaluating predictive performance across renewable-dominance regimes and applying SHAP analysis to identify the structural drivers of prediction difficulty in the Czech day-ahead market.

This study contributes to the literature in four ways:

- It evaluates predictive accuracy across four renewable-dominance regimes: solar-dominated, biomass-dominated, fossil-dominated, and mixed.
- It identifies the role of individual renewable technologies using SHAP-based explainability applied to a nonlinear forecasting model.
- It examines system-wide and pairwise interaction effects among renewable shares, load, imports, and lagged prices, guided by recent advances in explainable ML for energy systems.
- It analyses seasonal and intra-week dynamics to reveal how operational conditions influence price predictability.

Together, these contributions offer new insights into the mechanisms through which renewable penetration shapes predictive performance in thermally dominated electricity systems. While the empirical application focuses on Czechia, the regime-based and explainable framework is transferable to other electricity markets undergoing renewable-driven structural change. The remainder of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the data, preprocessing procedures, the forecasting models, feature construction, SHAP explainability approach and renewable-regime classification. Section 3 describes the empirical results. Section 4 discusses the findings and outlines their policy implications. Finally, section 5 concludes the study and outlines directions for future research.

2. Methodology

The flowchart of Fig. 1 summarizes the methodological framework used in this study. Hourly data from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform [26], including day-ahead prices, system load, generation by technology and cross-border flows, are first collected and preprocessed through cleaning and time alignment, with conservative handling of missing values and preserving extreme price spikes. Renewable-regime classification is then performed using hourly shares of solar, biomass and fossil generation. A threshold of 20% renewable share is used to identify renewable-dominant conditions, representing periods when renewable generation begins to play a meaningful role in price formation in the Czech electricity system.

To evaluate the robustness of this classification, additional sensitivity analysis was conducted using alternative thresholds ranging from 10% to 30%. Additional temporal, structural and cross-border features are constructed, including lagged prices, renewable and load interactions and RES share multiplied by net imports. Five forecasting models are implemented and evaluated using RMSE, MAE and MAPE, with regime-specific performance assessed separately. These metrics

Fig. 1. Methodological workflow for forecasting electricity prices under renewable penetration regimes.

measure electricity price predictability, defined as the ability of forecasting models to reproduce future price realizations, rather than the magnitude of price levels or the volatility of price fluctuations themselves. SHAP analysis provides model explainability by identifying important features, interaction effects and regime-dependent mechanisms. Insights from these steps support the interpretation of how renewable penetration shapes forecast difficulty and market behavior.

2.1. Study area: Czech electricity market

The Czech Republic operates a thermally dominated electricity system with coal, lignite, and nuclear plants forming the bulk of generation. Renewable energy contributions remain moderate, with solar and biomass as the main sources and minimal wind generation. Hydropower provides flexibility but limited total volume, and therefore plays a different role in system balancing [19].

The market is integrated into the European market-coupling framework, making the Czech system strongly affected by cross-border exchanges with Germany, Slovakia, Austria, and Poland. Such flows have been shown to significantly influence domestic price formation and volatility, particularly under changing renewable availability [24]. These characteristics make the Czech system an appropriate setting for

analyzing renewable-driven changes in price predictability.

Fig. 2 shows the evolution of hourly day-ahead market clearing prices in the Czech Republic during 2024. Prices exhibit substantial short-term volatility, with pronounced spikes during several periods of system stress, particularly in late summer and autumn. The annual mean price of 85.1 EUR/MWh masks strong intraday and seasonal fluctuations, including occasional negative prices and extreme upward excursions. This volatility reflects the interaction between demand variations, renewable generation availability, thermal dispatch constraints, and cross-border exchanges in a highly interconnected Central European market. These characteristics motivate the use of regime-aware and nonlinear forecasting approaches in the subsequent analysis.

Fig. 3 illustrates the evolution of system load in the Czech Republic during 2024, comparing actual demand with the corresponding day-ahead load forecasts. Fig. 3(a) shows a close alignment between forecast and realized load across the year, capturing both strong daily cycles and seasonal demand patterns. Fig. 3(b) reports the relative forecast error, which remains small on average, with a mean absolute percentage error of approximately 1.45%. While load forecasting accuracy is high, residual forecast errors persist and vary over time, particularly during periods of rapid demand changes. These residual uncertainties in demand forecasts interact with renewable generation variability and cross-

Day-Ahead Market Clearing Prices - Czech Republic

Fig. 2. Hourly day-ahead electricity market clearing prices in the Czech Republic in 2024.

System Load: Actual vs Forecast

Fig. 3. System load in the Czech Republic in 2024: actual demand and day-ahead load forecasts: (a) Hourly actual load and corresponding day-ahead forecasts, (b) Percentage forecast error.

border flows, contributing to the overall difficulty of day-ahead price prediction examined in this study.

Fig. 4 presents the hourly electricity generation mix in the Czech Republic in 2024. Nuclear generation provides a stable baseload throughout the year, while fossil-based generation, particularly lignite and gas, exhibits substantial variability to balance demand and system conditions. Renewable generation shows strong technology-specific patterns: solar output displays pronounced diurnal and seasonal variability, wind generation remains relatively modest and intermittent, and biomass contributes a comparatively stable but limited share.

Hydropower plays a minor and mostly flexible role. Overall, the Czech power system remains thermally dominated, with renewable sources introducing time-varying supply fluctuations that interact with demand and cross-border exchanges. This structural composition provides a suitable setting for examining how different renewable technologies affect day-ahead price predictability.

Fig. 5 illustrates the physical cross-border electricity flows between the Czech Republic and its main interconnected neighbors during 2024. The Czech system acts predominantly as a net exporter toward Austria and Slovakia, while exhibiting sustained net imports from Germany and

Fig. 4. Hourly electricity generation mix in the Czech Republic by technology in 2024.

Fig. 5. Physical cross-border electricity flows between the Czech Republic and neighboring markets in 2024.

Poland. These asymmetric and highly variable exchange patterns highlight the strong integration of the Czech electricity market within the Central European power system. The magnitude and volatility of cross-border flows indicate that domestic price formation is closely linked to regional balancing conditions, particularly under changing renewable availability. This interconnection reinforces the relevance of

incorporating cross-border imports and exports as explanatory features when assessing day-ahead price predictability.

2.2. Data collection, preprocessing, classification and featurng

The analysis uses one full year of hourly data for 2024 from the

ENTSO-E Transparency Platform [26], depicted in Figs. 2–5, which include:

- day-ahead market clearing prices
- system load
- disaggregated hourly generation (solar, biomass, wind, hydropower, fossil, waste-to-energy)
- physical cross-border imports and exports

Price and load data follow the standard reporting structures used in European markets [5]. Renewable shares are computed relative to total hourly generation, excluding hydropower when constructing renewable-regime classifications, in line with recent studies distinguishing dispatchable hydro from variability-driving renewables [26]. Each hour is assigned to one of four regimes:

- solar-dominated,
- biomass-dominated,
- fossil-dominated and
- mixed.

Renewable dominance regimes are defined based on hourly generation shares. A threshold of 20% renewable share is used to identify renewable-dominant conditions, reflecting the level at which renewable generation begins to have a meaningful influence on price dynamics in the Czech electricity system. For each hour, the regime is assigned according to the technology with the largest generation share. An hour is classified as solar-dominated or biomass-dominated when the respective renewable source has the highest share and the total renewable share exceeds the 20% threshold. Fossil-dominated hours correspond to cases where fossil generation represents the largest share of total generation. The mixed regime includes hours where no single technology clearly dominates or where renewable share remains below the threshold.

In cases where generation shares are very close, the classification follows the largest-share rule to ensure a consistent and mutually exclusive assignment. This structure follows prior work analyzing renewable impacts on electricity markets under different penetration levels [15,16]. To capture temporal, structural, and cross-border effects, additional features are constructed:

- lagged prices (1h, 24h, 168h), following standard forecasting practice [4],
- load–renewable interactions (e.g., solar \times load), capturing structural daytime patterns,
- RES_share \times net imports, reflecting cross-border smoothing or amplification dynamics [20] and
- load lags and renewable lags.

Missing values were handled conservatively as follows. Generation and physical cross-border flow series were converted to numeric and missing entries were set to zero only when a generation technology or flow route was not reported for a given hour, indicating no recorded production or flow. For price and load variables, no imputation was applied and observations required for lag construction were removed before model training. Extreme price events were preserved because they represent genuine market spikes and are central to understanding forecast difficulty under changing renewable conditions [3]. Such spikes often correspond to transitions between volatility regimes, reflecting structural shifts in market behavior under renewable variability [10]. The final dataset contains 8786 hourly observations for 2024 and 53 variables, including prices, load, energy generation by technology and physical cross-border flows. It is noted that a leap year normally contains 8784 h; the additional two observations reflect ENTSO-E time-stamp handling (for example, daylight-saving-time related reporting and boundary-hour records retained during data extraction and hourly alignment).

Although the study focuses on day-ahead electricity price prediction, the explanatory variables include realized values of system load, renewable generation, and cross-border flows obtained from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform. These variables are not fully available at the time of actual day-ahead forecasting. Therefore, the modeling framework is designed to analyze how renewable penetration influences forecast difficulty and price predictability under observed system conditions, rather than to replicate a fully operational forecasting setup based exclusively on *ex-ante* information. The results should thus be interpreted as a predictive analysis of price dynamics and forecast errors across renewable regimes.

2.3. Forecasting models (development and evaluation)

Five forecasting models are evaluated to compare predictive performance across renewable regimes: Persistence, Linear Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM. These models represent baseline, linear, and nonlinear machine learning approaches that are widely used in day-ahead electricity price forecasting and energy market analysis [4,5]. This selection covers baseline, linear, and nonlinear approaches commonly used in electricity price forecasting:

- **Persistence** predicts each hour's price as the previous hour's price and provides a benchmark for assessing the value of added model complexity.
- **Linear Regression** captures additive relationships between prices, load, renewable shares, and cross-border flows.
- **Random Forest** models nonlinear interactions and is used extensively in the explainability analysis because of its robust interpretability through SHAP values.
- **XGBoost** captures complex gradient-boosted tree interactions but may overfit in systems with limited renewable variability and noisy price spikes.
- **LightGBM** is a histogram-based gradient boosting method that can efficiently handle large feature sets and interaction effects, but it also shows signs of overfitting under the studied conditions.

Models are trained on 80% of the dataset and evaluated on 20% held-out data. A chronological split is applied to preserve the time-series structure and avoid data leakage. The training set covers the period from January 1, 2024 to October 19, 2024 (7028 observations), while the test set includes the remaining period from October 19, 2024 to December 31, 2024 (1758 observations). This approach ensures that only past information is used to predict future prices, consistent with standard practice in electricity price forecasting. The split is performed chronologically to avoid information leakage in the time-series setting, following standard practice in electricity price forecasting studies (e.g Ref. [27]). Specifically, the first 80% of observations (January–October 2024) are used for training, while the remaining 20% (October–December 2024) are reserved for out-of-sample testing. Performance metrics include RMSE, MAE, and MAPE, which remain standard in electricity price forecasting [4,5]. Following recent comparative studies on short-term price forecasting under high renewable variability [28], both linear and nonlinear models were included to capture different structural properties of the Czech market. Forecasting performance is evaluated:

- across renewable regimes,
- across price regimes,
- across seasons and
- under different system conditions.

Model configurations are specified as follows. Linear Regression is implemented without regularization, providing a baseline linear model. Random Forest is trained using 300 trees with a maximum depth of 12 to balance model complexity and computational efficiency. XGBoost uses

400 estimators with a learning rate of 0.05, maximum depth of 8, and a subsampling ratio of 0.9 to reduce overfitting. LightGBM employs 500 estimators with a learning rate of 0.03 and 80 leaf nodes, also with a subsampling ratio of 0.9. These parameter settings are selected based on standard practice for electricity price forecasting to balance computational efficiency with the ability to capture non-linear relationships. Feature construction, including lagged variables and interaction terms, is performed using only past information. No future values are used in model training or feature engineering, ensuring a consistent and leakage-free forecasting framework. This modeling design follows recent studies emphasizing the importance of data frequency and model selection in electricity price estimation, where machine learning approaches often outperform traditional econometric methods under high-frequency data conditions [29].

In addition to the primary chronological train–test split, an additional temporal validation strategy was applied to assess model stability over time. Specifically, rolling and expanding window evaluation schemes were employed, which are commonly applied in electricity market modeling and time-series validation studies [30]. This approach allows examination of performance consistency under evolving market conditions and varying data availability. The results of this additional validation are presented in Section 3.2.1.

2.4. Explainability framework (SHAP analysis)

To interpret model behavior, SHAP values are used to quantify the contribution of each feature to individual predictions. Global SHAP importance scores aim to identify the most influential variables, while dependence plots show how changes in renewable shares affect predicted prices [4]. This framework allows:

- quantification of each feature's contribution to model outputs,
- analysis of nonlinear response patterns to renewable shares and
- interaction effects such as:
 - o solar \times load: tests whether the load–price sensitivity changes under high solar output (daytime merit order effect).
 - o RES share \times net imports: tests whether imports stabilize or amplify prices depending on renewable availability (regional balancing and congestion).
 - o lagged price \times renewable output: tests state dependence, meaning renewable effects differ when the market is already in a high or low-price state.

A full SHAP interaction matrix is computed to reveal system-wide dependencies that influence price formation and forecast difficulty. This approach aligns with emerging best practices in explainable AI for energy systems, where SHAP is increasingly used to interpret deep and tree-based models [4,31].

2.5. Reproducibility

The empirical analysis has been designed to ensure reproducibility. All data were obtained from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform, and preprocessing steps including data cleaning, handling of missing values, feature construction, and renewable regime classification were explicitly described in Section 2.2. Model configurations and hyperparameters have been reported in Section 2.3. The models were implemented using standard machine learning libraries, and no proprietary data or custom algorithms were used. The training and testing split follows a chronological structure to avoid data leakage. The dataset used in this study is publicly available on Zenodo, and the corresponding access link is provided in the Data Availability Statement. The results can be replicated by following the procedures described in this paper.

3. Results and interpretation

3.1. Renewable energy shares and price dynamics

The distribution of technology-specific generation shares presented in Fig. 6 reveals clear structural differences in the Czech electricity mix. Solar generation has a wide and highly skewed distribution, with many hours clustered below 5 percent of total generation and a long tail in periods with strong irradiance. This pattern reflects its strong diurnal and seasonal dependence and the prevalence of hours with very low or zero output. Biomass displays a narrow and stable distribution centered around roughly 3–6 percent of total generation, which is consistent with its role as a dispatchable baseload source.

Hydro technologies (run-of-river, reservoir, and pumped storage) also show relatively tight distributions with limited variability. Their operation is largely governed by reservoir management and system balancing needs rather than short-term weather shocks. For this reason, hydro is included in Fig. 1 to provide a complete picture of the renewable mix, but it is not counted in the RES share variable used in the forecasting analysis in later sections. Taken together, these patterns shape the hourly price environment. Solar introduces a pronounced and predictable daytime cycle, biomass and hydro provide background stability, and the price signal is primarily driven by the interaction between variable solar output and the residual thermal generation fleet.

3.2. Impact of renewable mix on forecast difficulty

3.2.1. Overall model performance across the full dataset

To complement the regime-specific results, Table 1 reports the forecasting accuracy of each model over the full dataset without dividing hours by renewable regimes. This baseline comparison provides an assessment of how well each method performs under general operating conditions in the Czech electricity system.

Across all hours, Linear Regression achieves the best overall balance of accuracy and stability, outperforming the persistence benchmark in RMSE, MAE, and MAPE. This confirms that simple linear structure combined with lagged variables captures the dominant price dynamics. The persistence model remains a strong baseline because electricity prices exhibit strong autocorrelation, but it performs less effectively during volatile periods. Random Forest improves MAE relative to the persistence baseline but shows higher RMSE because tree-based models are more sensitive to rare price spikes. XGBoost and LightGBM deliver the weakest performance, which is consistent with their tendency to overfit in datasets with limited extreme events and high noise levels.

To assess whether these performance patterns are stable over time rather than specific to the chosen 80–20 train–test split, rolling and expanding window validation was conducted (Fig. 7). Rolling window validation with fixed 60-day test periods stepped weekly (28 windows) shows that Linear Regression outperforms Random Forest in the majority of temporal windows (approximately 75–80%). Both models exhibit degraded performance during late-2024 volatile periods (windows 22–28), although Linear Regression maintains a consistent advantage. Expanding window validation confirms that these patterns persist as the training set increases, suggesting that the observed performance differences are not driven by sample size limitations. The distribution of performance differences is skewed toward Linear Regression, indicating that the results reported in Table 1 are broadly representative across varying temporal conditions.

These findings support the conclusion that complex nonlinear models do not necessarily outperform simpler approaches in markets dominated by thermal generation and characterized by high volatility. They also provide a global benchmark that complements the regime-specific analysis in Section 3.2.2.

3.2.2. Comparative performance of all models across RES regimes

Table 2 presents the predictive performance of all five forecasting

Fig. 6. Distribution of renewable generation shares (solar, biomass, and hydro technologies) as kernel density estimates in the Czech power system.

Table 1

Overall forecasting performance across all hours.

Model	RMSE (EUR/MWh)	MAE (EUR/MWh)	MAPE (%)
Persistence	29.71	15.05	11.45
Linear Regression	28.54	14.58	12.23
Random Forest	36.26	15.61	11.35
XGBoost	40.05	16.44	11.82
LightGBM	42.37	16.77	11.72

models (Persistence, Linear Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM) across the four renewable-dominance regimes. The results outline clear and consistent patterns. Forecast accuracy is highest during solar-dominated hours, where all models achieve their lowest RMSE values. The strong daytime regularity of solar generation provides a predictable structure that improves model performance.

Biomass-dominated periods show moderate error levels. Biomass contributes stable output, which supports predictability, but its limited variability offers fewer dynamic signals for the models to learn. Forecast errors increase sharply in fossil-dominated hours, where RMSE values are the highest for every model. These hours are characterized by greater volatility in thermal generation and higher sensitivity to load swings, which reduce forecast reliability. The mixed regime falls between the two extremes, with intermediate accuracy that reflects partial renewable smoothing combined with residual demand uncertainty.

Across all models, the performance patterns are consistent. Forecast errors are lowest in solar-dominated regimes and highest in fossil-dominated regimes, indicating that renewable availability improves price predictability while fossil-dominant conditions increase forecast difficulty.

Linear Regression achieves the best overall forecasting performance across the full dataset, reflecting the strong autoregressive structure of electricity prices and the effectiveness of linear relationships under general system conditions. However, Random Forest performs comparably in renewable-dominated regimes, particularly during solar-dominated hours, where nonlinear interactions between renewable generation, load, and cross-border flows become more relevant.

Therefore, Random Forest is used for regime-specific analysis and

explainability, as it captures nonlinear interactions and supports SHAP-based interpretation of forecast drivers. This allows the study to investigate the mechanisms linking renewable penetration to price predictability without implying that Random Forest is the overall best-performing model.

To evaluate the robustness of the renewable regime classification, additional sensitivity analysis was conducted using alternative renewable-share thresholds ranging from 10% to 30%. The results indicate that forecasting performance remains stable across these alternative definitions. The overall RMSE varies between 36.58 and 38.40 EUR/MWh, corresponding to a relative sensitivity of 4.86%. The lowest RMSE occurs at the 20% threshold, which is therefore retained as the baseline regime definition. These results confirm that the main conclusions regarding the relationship between renewable penetration and forecast predictability are robust to reasonable changes in the regime classification.

Although Linear Regression achieves the best overall forecasting accuracy, Random Forest performs comparably in renewable-dominated regimes and is therefore used for regime-specific analysis due to its ability to capture nonlinear interactions. To formally assess whether these differences are statistically significant, Diebold–Mariano tests are conducted. The results are presented in Table 3.

The Diebold–Mariano test results in Table 3 provide a formal statistical comparison of forecast accuracy between Random Forest and Linear Regression. The results confirm that Linear Regression significantly outperforms Random Forest in the overall dataset, as well as in fossil-dominated and mixed regimes ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, the differences between the two models are not statistically significant in solar- and biomass-dominated regimes. This indicates that both models perform similarly when renewable generation plays a dominant role in price formation. These findings reinforce that model performance is regime-dependent. Linear models provide strong baseline performance across all conditions, while nonlinear models such as Random Forest offer comparable accuracy in renewable-dominated regimes and are better suited for capturing interaction effects and supporting explainability analysis.

Fig. 7. Temporal validation via rolling and expanding window cross-validation. Comparison of Linear Regression and Random Forest across 28 temporal windows. (a) Rolling window RMSE over time. (b) Rolling window performance difference (RF - LR), with green shading indicating Linear Regression superiority in ~75-80% of windows. (c) Expanding window RMSE showing consistent patterns. (d) Distribution of performance differences demonstrating Linear Regression's systematic temporal advantage. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 2

Comparative forecasting performance across renewable-dominance regimes. RMSE and MAE are reported in EUR/MWh, while MAPE is reported in percent (%). N_{hours} denotes the number of hourly observations in each regime.

Model	RES regime	N -hours	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
Persistence	Solar-dominated	208	12.55	9.19	9.38
Persistence	Biomass-dominated	331	13.98	9.59	13.85
Persistence	Fossil-dominated	887	38.81	19.54	11.86
Persistence	Mixed	298	17.23	11.85	9.01
Linear Regression	Solar-dominated	208	11.38	8.49	8.87
Linear Regression	Biomass-dominated	331	14.55	9.94	19.37
Linear Regression	Fossil-dominated	887	37.30	18.91	11.53
Linear Regression	Mixed	298	15.69	11.07	8.70
Random Forest	Solar-dominated	208	10.97	8.44	8.38
Random Forest	Biomass-dominated	331	14.53	9.81	15.66
Random Forest	Fossil-dominated	887	48.53	20.57	11.08
Random Forest	Mixed	298	16.58	12.32	9.45
XGBoost	Solar-dominated	208	12.43	9.44	8.81
XGBoost	Biomass-dominated	331	15.13	10.05	17.65
XGBoost	Fossil-dominated	887	53.71	21.83	11.35
XGBoost	Mixed	298	18.16	12.39	8.88
LightGBM	Solar-dominated	208	12.04	8.83	8.34
LightGBM	Biomass-dominated	331	15.18	9.97	16.52
LightGBM	Fossil-dominated	887	57.13	22.47	11.47
LightGBM	Mixed	298	17.68	12.85	9.52

Table 3

Statistical comparison of forecast accuracy using Diebold–Mariano tests (95% confidence intervals).

Regime	N	RF RMSE	LR RMSE	Difference	95% CI	p-value	Winner
Overall	1724	37.30	28.68	+8.62	[8.00, 9.24]	<0.001***	LR
Solar-dominated	208	10.97	11.38	-0.41	[-1.02, 0.20]	0.186 n.s.	Tie
Biomass-dominated	331	14.53	14.55	-0.02	[-0.65, 0.61]	0.950 n.s.	Tie
Fossil-dominated	887	48.53	37.30	+11.23	[10.10, 12.36]	<0.001***	LR
Mixed	298	16.58	15.69	+0.89	[0.16, 1.62]	0.017**	LR

3.3. Relationship between RES share and prediction error

3.3.1. Forecast accuracy by RES regime

Forecast errors from the Random Forest model vary substantially across renewable dominance regimes (Fig. 8). Solar-dominated hours have the lowest prediction errors, with tight distributions and very few outliers. Biomass-dominated and mixed regimes show moderate accuracy. Fossil-dominated hours produce the highest errors, including extreme outliers above 500 EUR/MWh. These results confirm that higher renewable penetration, especially solar, reduces forecast uncertainty. Fossil-heavy hours create larger forecasting challenges because of volatile load patterns and thermal generation constraints.

3.3.2. Analysis of RES share and Random Forest forecast error

Fig. 9 shows a clear negative association between renewable share and forecast error. Very large errors, often above 100 EUR/MWh, occur almost entirely when the RES share is below 5 percent. When renewable penetration increases beyond 10–15 percent, forecast errors become consistently lower and more stable. This indicates that higher renewable availability stabilizes day-ahead price formation. This pattern shows that forecast errors decrease as renewable share increases.

3.3.3. Forecast error patterns across price regimes and RES regimes

To better understand how forecast difficulty varies under different

Fig. 8. Random Forest absolute forecast error across RES regimes (boxplots).

Fig. 9. RES share vs. Random Forest absolute forecast error, with fitted regression trendline.

market conditions, Fig. 10 compares mean absolute forecast error across four price regimes (very low, low, medium, and high prices) and four renewable-dominance regimes. This two-dimensional perspective provides additional insight beyond the RES-share and model-level analyses.

The results show that forecast errors remain relatively low and stable across all RES regimes when prices fall within the very low, low, or medium ranges. Solar-dominated hours consistently exhibit the lowest errors, which reflects the stabilizing influence of predictable daytime solar output. Biomass-dominated periods also show relatively low errors due to their stable baseload characteristics.

The largest differences emerge during high-price hours. Fossil-dominated periods display the highest error levels, with mean absolute errors approaching 40 EUR/MWh, confirming that price spikes are the primary source of forecasting difficulty. Biomass-dominated hours also experience increased errors during high-price conditions, although the magnitude is notably smaller. In contrast, solar-dominated hours maintain substantially lower error levels even during price spikes.

These findings highlight an important interaction effect: renewable-rich periods not only reduce average price volatility but also make prices more predictable. High-price events occur disproportionately during

Fig. 10. Mean absolute forecast error across price regimes and RES regimes (heatmap).

fossil-dominated hours, which explains both the elevated error levels and the reduced performance of forecasting models in those conditions.

3.3.4. Interaction effects: RES share and cross-border imports

To understand how renewable availability interacts with system balancing conditions, SHAP interaction values were computed for the term RES share × Net import. Fig. 11 illustrates how the combined effect of renewable penetration and cross-border flows contributes to Random Forest predictions. The interaction pattern reveals three important insights:

1. Low-RES share amplifies the impact of imports on prices: when RES share is below approximately 10%, the interaction values cluster near zero but with greater variability. Hours with strong net imports (blue points) tend to have slightly negative interaction contributions, while hours with net exports (pink points) lean positive. This indicates that when domestic renewables are scarce, the system becomes more sensitive to cross-border balancing, which increases the difficulty of predicting prices.

2. Higher RES share reduces volatility and weakens import effects: as RES share increases beyond 15% interaction values converge toward a narrow band around zero. This suggests that abundant domestic renewables reduce reliance on imports and exports, lowering the marginal influence of cross-border exchanges on price formation. The system becomes more self-sufficient, resulting in more stable and predictable model behavior.
3. Extreme interaction values occur only when both RES share is low and imports are large: the lower-left region of the plot shows occasional strong negative interaction values associated with large net imports. These conditions correspond to scarcity episodes that are difficult for any model to forecast accurately. The interaction analysis highlights that these episodes are driven not only by low renewables, but also by sudden import requirements.

Overall, the interaction effects confirm that renewable availability plays a stabilizing role not only through its direct impact on price levels, but also by moderating the influence of cross-border flows. This supports the broader conclusion that higher renewable penetration improves price predictability in the Czech system.

3.3.5. Global interaction strengths among electricity market features

To complement the pairwise SHAP analyses, Fig. 12 presents a heatmap of mean SHAP interaction values across all major market variables. The matrix highlights how strongly each feature interacts with others in shaping price predictions. As expected, the dominant interaction occurs between lagged prices, confirming that autocorrelation remains the most influential structure in the Czech day-ahead market. However, several renewable-related interactions also appear consistently. The RES share × Price (t-1) and Solar share × Load interactions exhibit non-negligible values, supporting the earlier finding that renewable penetration modifies the sensitivity of prices to load and past price signals. Interactions involving net imports are weaker but still detectable, which aligns with the limited but meaningful role of cross-border balancing in the Czech power system.

Overall, the heatmap provides a system-level overview showing that while price autocorrelation dominates model behavior, renewable integration introduces secondary but important interaction pathways that shape price dynamics under varying system conditions.

Fig. 11. SHAP interaction values for RES share × Net Import in the Random Forest model.

Fig. 12. SHAP interaction heatmap showing the strength of pairwise feature interactions in the electricity price model.

3.4. Explainability analysis (SHAP)

SHAP analysis was used to interpret the Random Forest model and identify the main drivers of predicted prices (Figs. 13 and 14). The SHAP summary plot in Fig. 8 shows that lagged prices (1 h, 24 h, 168 h) are the most influential variables, which reflects the strong autoregressive structure of electricity markets. Among non-price variables, Solar share, the Solar \times Load interaction term, Renewable share, and Net import form the most important explanatory group. These results confirm that both renewable availability and cross-border exchanges influence price formation in addition to past price behavior. Definitions of features are

Fig. 13. SHAP summary plot for the Random Forest model (top features).

described in Table 4.

The dependence plots in Fig. 14 provides further insights. Solar share shows a strong non-linear pattern. At very low solar levels the model attributes upward pressure on prices. As the solar share increases, SHAP values fall, indicating a price-depressing effect that aligns with mid-day merit order shifts. Biomass share has a narrow SHAP range close to zero, which suggests that biomass mainly acts as a stable and predictable baseload component. Wind share has almost no SHAP variation, confirming that current wind penetration in the Czech system is too small to influence prices. Finally, Renewable share shows a clear and monotonic decline in SHAP values, meaning that higher overall renewable penetration is consistently associated with lower predicted prices and reduced uncertainty.

Overall, SHAP results show that solar provides the strongest renewable signal for price forecasting. Biomass contributes stability but little variability and wind remains negligible under current conditions.

3.5. Seasonal predictability

Seasonal conditions have a significant effect on forecast accuracy (Fig. 15). Winter exhibits the highest error levels, with a large number of extreme outliers above 400–500 EUR/MWh. These outcomes reflect strong heating demand, reduced solar availability, and frequent price spikes during cold months. In contrast, autumn shows the lowest errors, with a narrow distribution and very few extreme observations. Load conditions are more stable during this season, and renewable generation aligns more smoothly with demand. These results confirm that price predictability improves during periods with higher renewable availability and lower volatility in system load.

3.6. Weekly patterns and renewable signals

Fig. 16 provides a weekly view of day-ahead prices and normalized generation shares from solar, wind, and biomass. Solar output displays a

Fig. 14. SHAP dependence plots for (a) Solar share, (b) Biomass share, (c) Wind share, and (d) Renewable share, colored by Price(t-1).

Table 4

Definitions of features used in SHAP analysis.

Feature	Meaning
Price (t-1)	Day-ahead price 1 h earlier
Price (t-24)	Day-ahead price 24 h earlier
Price (t-168)	Day-ahead price 168 h earlier
Solar × Load	Interaction between solar share and system load
Renewable share	Share of total generation from renewable sources
Solar share	Share of generation from solar PV
Net imports	Physical cross-border net imports (MW)
Load (t-24)	System load 24 h earlier
Load (t-168)	System load 168 h earlier
Forecast load	Day-ahead total load forecast
RES × Import	Interaction between renewable share and net imports
Hour of day	Hourly time index (0–23)
Day of week	Day of the week (1–7)
Month	Calendar month (1–12)
Actual load	Actual measured load (MW)

distinct and regular daily cycle, which aligns closely with mid-day price troughs and reinforces its role as the strongest structural signal in the Czech market. Biomass exhibits a flat and consistent profile, contributing to system stability but offering little variation. Wind shares remain very low and irregular, confirming their limited influence under current penetration levels. This visualization reinforces earlier findings that Solar acts as a strong structural signal, Biomass provides baseload stability and Wind plays a minimal role under current Czech market conditions. Together, these results demonstrate that renewable penetration, especially solar, significantly enhances price predictability in the Czech day-ahead market, while fossil-dominated hours remain the primary source of forecast uncertainty.

3.7. Robustness analysis

To evaluate the reliability of the empirical findings, additional robustness analyses have been conducted. These include sensitivity tests for missing-value treatment and renewable-share thresholds, as well as validation of model performance stability.

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the impact of alternative missing-value treatments in Table 5. Three approaches are compared in terms of zero replacement, dropping missing observations, and linear interpolation. The results show that model performance (measured by forecast errors) varies only marginally across these approaches. The RMSE ranges from 37.30 to 38.41 EUR/MWh, corresponding to a relative difference of approximately 3%, while MAE remains similarly stable. These findings indicate that the empirical results are robust to alternative missing-value treatments.

To assess the robustness of the renewable regime definition, a sensitivity analysis was conducted using alternative renewable-share thresholds. The corresponding results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 presents the sensitivity of forecasting performance to alternative renewable-share thresholds. The results show that overall RMSE varies only moderately across thresholds, with differences below 5%, indicating that the main findings are robust to the choice of threshold.

At lower thresholds (10–15%), renewable-dominant conditions occur more frequently but may include hours with weaker renewable influence. At higher thresholds (25–30%), the number of high-renewable observations becomes very limited, which leads to artificially low RMSE values and reduces statistical reliability. Therefore, a 20% threshold is selected as a balanced definition that captures meaningful renewable dominance while ensuring sufficient sample size and stable model performance.

To further assess model generalization and potential overfitting, a

Fig. 15. Random Forest absolute forecast error across seasons (boxplots).

Fig. 16. Weekly evolution of day-ahead prices and scaled renewable shares (solar, wind, biomass).

Table 5
Sensitivity of forecasting performance to missing-value treatment.

Missing-value treatment	RMSE (EUR/MWh)	MAE (EUR/MWh)
Zero replacement	37.30	16.00
Drop missing rows	38.41	16.16
Linear interpolation	37.32	16.02

Table 6
Sensitivity of forecasting performance to renewable-share threshold.

Threshold (%)	Overall RMSE (EUR/MWh)	High-renewable RMSE (EUR/MWh)	Low-renewable RMSE (EUR/MWh)
10	37.43	13.01	39.63
15	37.49	12.88	38.43
20	36.58	15.78	36.94
25	38.40	9.14	38.51
30	37.65	1.14	37.69

comparison of training and testing errors has been conducted and the corresponding results are presented in Table 7.

The comparison of training and testing errors highlights differences in model generalization. Linear Regression shows a relatively small gap between training and testing performance, indicating stable generalization. In contrast, tree-based models such as Random Forest, XGBoost,

Table 7
Training vs testing performance comparison.

Model	Train RMSE	Test RMSE	Δ RMSE	RMSE Ratio
Linear Regression	16.57	28.97	12.40	1.75
Random Forest	6.21	37.67	31.46	6.06
XGBoost	1.96	40.97	39.01	20.90
LightGBM	5.28	43.46	38.17	8.23
Persistence (Naive baseline)	-	29.60	-	-

and LightGBM exhibit larger gaps, reflecting higher sensitivity to noise and extreme price spikes in the dataset. These results suggest that while nonlinear models can capture complex patterns, their out-of-sample performance may be affected by data variability. Despite this, Random Forest is retained for regime-specific analysis because it captures nonlinear interactions that are central to understanding renewable-driven price dynamics. Its use in this study focuses on interpretability and interaction analysis rather than purely on predictive accuracy.

4. Discussion and policy implications

The results of this study demonstrate that renewable energy penetration plays a central role in shaping the predictability of day-ahead electricity prices in the Czech energy market. Solar generation shows the strongest association with forecasting accuracy. Its predictable diurnal pattern and concentrated daytime output contribute to reduced volatility and improved model performance. Hours with high solar shares consistently show smaller forecast errors, while fossil-dominated hours exhibit the highest errors and frequent extreme price events. These findings confirm that renewable availability can reduce market uncertainty even in systems where thermal units remain the dominant source of electricity. Importantly, the results relate to improvements in price predictability, measured through forecasting errors, rather than direct reductions in price levels or volatility themselves.

These results can be interpreted through three complementary mechanisms frequently discussed in electricity market literature. First, the merit-order effect implies that low-marginal-cost renewable generation, particularly solar, shifts the supply curve and compresses price variability during hours with abundant renewable output. This produces more structured and predictable price patterns during daylight hours. Second, electricity prices exhibit strong autoregressive behavior, meaning that lagged prices contain substantial information about future price formation. When renewable output follows relatively stable diurnal patterns, the interaction between lagged prices and renewable generation can reinforce predictable price dynamics. Third, the results highlight the importance of regime dependence, where forecasting performance varies across system states defined by different generation mixes. Under renewable-dominant regimes, price formation tends to follow more systematic patterns, whereas fossil-dominant regimes are more sensitive to demand shocks, fuel costs, and balancing requirements, which increases forecast difficulty.

Biomass behaves as a stable baseload technology and provides modest but consistent support to system predictability. Its contribution does not alter price formation as strongly as solar, yet biomass-dominated hours produce lower forecast errors than fossil-dominated hours. Wind, by contrast, remains too limited in the Czech power system to influence day-ahead price behavior, but its role may increase as capacity expands in future years.

SHAP analyses provide insight into how the forecasting model responds to different explanatory variables and interaction effects. The effect of solar share interacts strongly with load, indicating that solar generation appears to reshape the traditional load–price relationship by reducing the marginal cost of meeting demand during daylight hours. Interactions between renewable share and net physical imports indicate that forecast difficulty varies depending on the availability of domestic renewable generation and the role of cross-border balancing flows. These patterns help explain why forecasting performance differs across operating conditions without implying direct causal changes in market behavior. The observed relationships are consistent with merit-order effects and regime-dependent price dynamics discussed in the electricity market literature. These observed relationships are consistent with the merit-order mechanism and regime-dependent price dynamics observed in European electricity markets. These findings may differ from renewable-dominated electricity systems such as Denmark or Germany, where higher shares of variable renewable energy, particularly wind, introduce greater short-term variability and forecasting

uncertainty, highlighting the importance of system structure in shaping price predictability.

While Linear Regression shows the strongest overall predictive performance, Random Forest is used for model interpretation because it captures nonlinear relationships and interaction effects among renewable shares, load, imports, and lagged prices. Tree-based ensemble models are particularly suitable for SHAP analysis because they allow detailed decomposition of feature importance and interaction effects. In this study, Random Forest therefore serves as an interpretable nonlinear benchmark that helps explain regime-dependent forecasting behavior. It is important to note that SHAP explanations reflect the structure of the underlying model and should therefore be interpreted as model-based insights rather than direct evidence of structural market mechanisms.

This study is based on hourly data from a single year (2024). This period was characterized by relatively high volatility in European electricity markets due to ongoing structural adjustments in fuel markets, renewable integration, and cross-border electricity flows. As a result, the empirical results may partly reflect year-specific market conditions. While the identified relationships between renewable penetration and forecast predictability provide useful insights, they should be interpreted with appropriate caution. Future research should extend the analysis to multi-year datasets in order to evaluate the temporal stability of the observed regime-dependent patterns. In addition, the use of realized explanatory variables, including load, generation, and cross-border flows, implies that the analysis reflects predictive relationships under observed system conditions rather than a strict operational day-ahead forecasting setup based solely on *ex-ante* information. The Czech electricity system also shares structural characteristics with several Central and Eastern European electricity markets, including a high share of thermal generation, increasing solar deployment, and strong cross-border interconnections. These similarities suggest that the regime-based forecasting framework may be applicable to comparable electricity systems, although empirical verification across multiple markets would be required.

From an economic perspective, these findings have important implications for electricity market efficiency, system operation costs, and resource allocation. The results also have implications for forecasting practice and operational planning in electricity markets. First, the findings suggest that periods with higher solar generation tend to exhibit more predictable price dynamics, which may support improved forecasting performance for market participants and system operators. From a system operation perspective, the results have direct implications for transmission system operators (TSOs) in planning reserve and balancing capacities. The findings show that solar-dominated regimes are associated with lower forecast errors and more stable price dynamics, reflecting improved predictability of supply conditions. This enhanced predictability can reduce the uncertainty faced by TSOs in real-time system balancing and may allow for more efficient allocation of reserve capacity. In particular, lower forecast uncertainty implies a reduced need for precautionary reserve margins, which can translate into lower balancing and regulating costs. Conversely, fossil-dominated regimes exhibit higher volatility and forecast errors, requiring more conservative reserve procurement and increasing operational costs. These results suggest that increasing the share of predictable renewable sources, such as solar, can support not only decarbonization objectives but also improve operational efficiency in electricity markets by reducing balancing requirements and associated system costs. The growing deployment of battery energy storage systems (BESS) in the Czech electricity system may further influence these patterns in the future. By storing excess solar generation during daylight hours and shifting it to periods of higher demand, BESS can enhance system flexibility, smooth price fluctuations, and potentially modify the observed relationship between renewable penetration and forecast predictability.

Second, the stabilizing role of biomass generation indicates that dispatchable renewable technologies can contribute to more structured price patterns during periods of low solar availability. Third, the

observed interactions between renewable generation and cross-border imports highlight the importance of considering regional electricity exchanges when designing forecasting models for interconnected markets. These insights are particularly relevant for forecasting system operators and energy traders seeking to improve prediction accuracy under different renewable penetration regimes. Finally, the results indicate that forecasting tools used by market operators and energy traders should incorporate renewable-specific regime analysis and explainability techniques. Understanding how renewable output interacts with load and imports can improve forecasting under extreme conditions, particularly during periods with low renewable availability.

It is important to note that renewable dominance regimes in this study are defined using realized generation shares, which are endogenous outcomes influenced by weather conditions, demand patterns, and system constraints. As a result, the analysis identifies statistical associations between renewable penetration and price predictability, as measured by forecasting errors, rather than causal effects. Seasonal demand patterns, renewable availability, and cross-border balancing conditions may also influence both generation shares and price dynamics. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as evidence of regime-dependent forecasting behavior rather than causal impacts of specific renewable technologies.

5. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of how renewable energy penetration influences the predictability of day-ahead electricity prices in the Czech electricity market. Using four forecasting models and a detailed explainability framework, the results indicate that higher renewable shares, particularly solar generation, lead to substantially lower forecast errors. Renewable-dominant conditions improve price predictability, while fossil-dominant periods remain the most difficult to forecast. These results therefore relate primarily to electricity price predictability, measured through forecasting performance, rather than directly estimating the effects of renewable penetration on price levels or volatility.

Random Forest provides an interpretable nonlinear framework that helps explain the observed forecasting patterns. Renewable availability is associated with a reduced influence of lagged prices and lower sensitivity to load and cross-border imports in the forecasting models. Interaction analyses further show that solar output plays a structural role in shaping price dynamics, and renewable share stabilizes the system by reducing dependence on external balancing.

Seasonal and weekly patterns reinforce these findings. Predictability is highest during periods with moderate load and consistent renewable output, while winter conditions generate the most uncertainty. Together, the results highlight the value of renewable expansion for improving system stability and reducing market volatility.

Although the empirical analysis focuses on Czechia, the mechanisms identified are also relevant to other thermally dominated and interconnected electricity markets with similar characteristics, such as moderate renewable penetration, strong cross-border interconnections, and significant thermal generation capacity. The regime-based and explainable framework can support system operators and market participants by enabling regime-aware forecasting and more targeted integration strategies. Future research will extend this work by incorporating probabilistic forecasting, analyzing extreme event behavior, or comparing results across multiple interconnected European markets. As renewable capacity increases across Europe, understanding the mechanisms that govern price predictability will remain essential for market design, system operation, and investment planning.

Data statement

The dataset used in this study will be openly available on Zenodo under a CC BY 4.0 license at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17866870>.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Libor Štěpanec: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Eftichios Koutroulis:** Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Hnin Yee Aye:** Data curation, Investigation, Software, Writing – review & editing. **Ohn Zin Lin:** Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Dagmar Juchelkova:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Given his role as Associate Editor, Eftichios Koutroulis had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to another journal editor. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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